

TEACHING AND LEARNING APPROACHES ABOUT COMMUNICATIVE SKILLS IN ENGLISH LANGUAGE

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Annotation : Teaching and learning communicative skills in foreign languages is so important and easy way to keep in touch with nations. Also that purpose is the main point to learn speaking English .

There are some of helpful approaches to learn strongly deeply and faster that can be so effectively to learners . All method that use in this way organized and studied from science . In the article I examined some of beneficial hints about teaching and learning communicative skills. While this article produced remarkable notes belong to increase your four skills and using in real life or oral speech.

Keywords: Communication , psychological , narration , conversation , approaches , contextualized. I am basically write about one of the aspects which should be take into accounts . The communicative aspect is also so long important branch of learning English language. Speaking as a skill of oral communication is considered one of the speech activities.

Speaking as a skill of oral communication is considered one of the speech activities. Psychological content of speaking is expressing ideas. In a simpler way speaking as a methodological concept envelops: 1) the process of expressing idea; 2) utterance; 3)

oral speech; 4) statement. Answering a question or even a whole monologue can be the expression of idea. So speaking is an integral part of oral conversation. Speaking is the use of a certain lexical, grammatical or phonetic phenomena in the aim of expressing the idea. The proverb «First think then speak» proves this idea. So verbalization of ideas is speaking skill. Speaker chooses ready word or grammatical units from the

memory. Usually materials of mother tongue are always ready in memory. However is observed (order of words in a foreign language and mother tongue). Speaking skill should be taught integratively with other skills (writing, listening and reading).

We can express our opinion verbally/orally in two ways namely monologue and dialogue. Teaching monologue and dialogue is one of the main requirements of the curriculum. According to ideas of some foreign language psychologists, Speaking is not either a communication process or utterance but it is a means

of statement or expression of the idea. There are certain genres of conversation. Speaking in the English language has been considered the most widely spread portion of learning English. Challenging of the four skills given the fact that it involves a complex process of constructing meaning. This process requires speakers to make decisions about why, how and when to communicate depending on the cultural and social context in which the speaking act occurs. Additionally, it involves a dynamic interrelation between speakers and hearers that results in their simultaneous interaction of producing and processing spoken discourse under time constraints. speaking as an interactive, social and contextualized communicative event. Therefore, the key role of the speaking skill in developing learners communicative competence has also become evident, since this skill requires learners to be in possession of knowledge about how to produce not only linguistically correct but also pragmatically appropriate utterances. Drawing on these considerations, this subtheme first outlines the advances that have been made in learning the skill of speaking over the last decades. It then considers how this knowledge becomes the basis for teaching speaking from a communicative perspective. Finally, it presents the importance of integrating this skill within a communicative competence framework so that learners can acquire their English language. Audiolingual teaching approach. This instructional method emphasized the importance of starting with the teaching of oral skills, rather than the written ones, by applying the fixed order of listening-speaking-reading-writing for each structure. Thus, learners were engaged in a series of activities, such as exercises and substitution exercises, which focused on repeating grammatical structures and patterns through intense aural-oral practice. However, rather than fostering spoken interaction, this type of oral activities was simply a way of teaching pronunciation skills and grammatical accuracy. Consequently, although it can be assumed that this approach to learning and teaching speaking stressed the development of oral skills, speaking was merely considered as an effective medium for providing language input and facilitating memorization rather than as a discourse skill in its own right. In fact, significant aspects, such as the role that internal mental processes play when learning to produce new and more complex grammatical structures, were neglected under this view. The task of paying attention to those processes was the focus of study in the all aspects. Knowledge of non-verbal means of communication (i.e., body language, facial expressions, eye contact, etc.) is also of paramount importance to communicate appropriately when producing a spoken

text. Speakers need to pay careful attention to listeners' non-verbal movements, such as their body language or whether to maintain or avoid eye contact, in order to be able to repair their intervention if something goes wrong in the course of the exchange. Dialogue and monologue are taught together in practice of teaching but their teaching methods are looked through separately. If we compare these two types of speech with each other we can see exact difference between them. The following types of dialogue are recommended to teach at secondary schools:

1. Information - exchange dialogue.
2. Plan - dialogue (outlined in order to work together).
3. Discussion - dialogue. To speak one's own ideas.

Each of them involves private language material and may belong to different stages of education. In the information- exchange speech the interlocutors will exchange concrete information with each other. Its aim is to inform interlocutors mutually or unilaterally (one-sided) and it is used at initial stage of education because of being capable to utilize ordinary and less language materials. Whereas plan - dialogue is much more complicated in the form and deeper in the meaning. That's why the learner should know future simple tense, imperative sentences, how to refuse his/her interlocutor's opinion and to know how to defend his/her ideas in plan - dialogue. It is suitable at the middle stage of education. While complementing discussion - dialogue it is demanded to know subordinate clauses which linked due to relation of cause and effect and to be able to use different means of modals. While using discussion - dialogue it is indispensable to know how to prove his/her opinion, how to persuade his/her interlocutor, to be critical and to find and prove faults. The attention of the speaker is given to the core of speech. Speech experiences become developed. Discussion - pair speech is used at higher levels (lyceum and colleges). Dialogue is taught in two ways: deductive (from general to private) and inductive (from private to general). Learning and teaching communicative skills you can choose the best suitable method or activities according to your ability and weak and strength point of your study. Especially all students have their own learning skill. It would be auditory learner, kinesthetic learner or visual learner in this point you should select the best method of gain speaking skills method. In this way you can improve your communicative skills very high quality and easier.

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